

A Brief Review on Microplastic Pollution in Aquatic Body

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Abstract:

The extent of microplastics in water body is a recent challenge in the field of environment. The issue has become aggravated particularly after COVID-19 due to the excessive use of plastic PPEs including face masks, gloves as per Government and WHO instructions. COVID-19 pandemic also caused a spike in the demand for home delivery packaged vegetables, groceries and many necessary items. This not only resulted in increased consumption of plastic materials but also generated huge amount of plastic waste. These plastic particles enter the aquatic system through different routes like effluent discharge from waste water treatment plants, rain water runoff, agricultural runoff, direct littering, and eventually reach the ocean via rivers and sea. Thus ocean basins become the ultimate sink for microplastics. The widespread transport of microplastics on land and aquatic medium is due to their physical characteristics like shape, small size and low density. At the same time, the durability, stability, slow degradation kinetics, long residence time in aquatic body, high ratio of surface area to volume, ability to adsorb toxic materials from surroundings and subsequent release of the materials in aquatic media make the microplastics a potent vector of different diseases. Microplastics may induce different detrimental effects on aquatic organisms which include embryotoxicity, neurotoxicity, behavioral changes, biochemical and hematological changes. Owing to the size similarity with plankton, microplastics are ingested by aquatic organisms of different trophic levels and ultimately enters into the human body through food chain. The entry of microplastics with food can also pose a significant effects on human body. Major sources of microplastics in human body are table salts, drinking water and sea food. Thus microplastics may risk not only aquatic organisms but also can be a threat of human life. It is seen from several studies that biological effects of microorganisms depend on shape, size, composition and physical characteristics of microplastics. Therefore control of microplastics in aquatic body is very much needed. Conventional primary and secondary treatments can remove major portion of microplastics but incorporation of advanced treatment processes increases the overall removal efficiency. However, complete removal of microplastics in final discharge of waste water treatment plant is still awaited and also microplastics removed from the waste water treatment plant often return to the environment through sludge. This invites more study and research work in this area. This paper presents a brief discussion on the 1) sources of microplastics in aquatic body, 2) toxicity of microplastics on aquatic organisms, 3) a summary of different methods reported to remove microplastics from aquatic body.

Keywords: Microplastics, Environment, Aquatic Body, Aquatic organisms, Toxicity, Microplastics removal methods

1. Introduction

Plastic particles with size between 1nm and 5mm are generally referred to as Microplastics (GESAMP 2015). Depending on their mode of generation, they are named as Primary microplastics and secondary microplastics. Primary microplastics enter into the environment during the course of their production. On the other hand secondary ones are introduced in the environment by the process of weathering or degradation of larger plastics objects. They have varying colors, compositions, densities and they differ in their origin as well. Major raw polymers present in different types of plastics are polyethylene, polypropylene, polyurethane, polystyrene, polyesters, polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polyvinylchloride (PVC) and polyamide. The amount of plastic debris which disposes to marine system per year is around 5 to 13 million (Wang et al. 2019). Usage of disposable PPE made of plastics has increased

microplastics pollution during COVID-19. About 0.15 to 0.39 million tons of plastics waste generated in a year out of face mask only is likely to pollute the global ocean after COVID-19 (Chowdhury et al 2021).

Once the plastics are released in the environment through different processes and activities, they may be transferred to lakes, rivers and eventually end up at sea and oceans by wind movement and ocean currents. The amount of marine litter that originates from land-based sources is around 80% (Jang et al. 2020). The extent and nature of microplastics contained in water body depends on various factors, e.g. its proximity to urban region, population of nearby areas. It also is influenced by hydrological and meteorological parameters. Besides, Industrial and domestic waste water is a significant source of microplastics pollution in water bodies.. Removal rate, shape, size of microplastics originated from a waste water treatment plant can vary depending on the applied treatment techniques (Elizalde-Velázquez G.A. and Gómez-Oliván L.M. 2021).

The widespread dispersal of microplastics on land and aquatic systems is due to their lightweight, small size and diversity in shapes. (Horton and Dixon 2018). Microplastics having polythelene, polypropylene component have less density in comparison with marine water, so they float and affect the oceanic surfaces. Materials with higher density sink and affect bottom of the ocean (Horton et al. 2017).

The ubiquity of microplastics in marine systems and also in freshwater can cause significant harm on aquatic organisms. This includes biochemical and hematological changes, embryotoxicity, neurotoxicity, behavioral changes, histopathological damage (Hamed et al. 2019 and Li et al. 2020). The organisms of different tropic levels intake the microplastics as their food due to size similarity with plankton and thus by the process of biomagnifications ultimately the plastic particles can enter into the human body (Hwang et al. 2019).

Removal of microplastics from aquatic body includes physical, chemical as well as biological ingestion methods. Primary and secondary treatment processes in a typical procedure of wastewater treatment can remove major portion of microplastics, though incorporation of advanced treatment increases removal efficiency (Talvitie et al 2017, Ziajahromi et al 2017). It has been seen from several studies that sorption and filtration are two important physical processes that effectively remove microplastics from aquatic body. The aim of this study is to provide an overall idea on the sources of microplastics in the water body. It also aims to provide an overview of the level of toxicity and also of different removal methods of microplastics from water.

2. Methodology

A systemic literature review was carried out using the scientific database (specifically Google Scholar, Science direct) to collect the existing literature on microplastic pollution in aquatic body for last six years (2017-2022). The keywords used for search were microplastics, aquatic body, or microplastics removal methods. The search resulted more than 70 papers. 20 papers were considered relevant to the objective of this study based on the abstract, conclusion and also the contents of papers.

3. Sources

Major sources of microplastics in aquatic body are domestic sewage treatment plants, agricultural runoff, urban waste and fishing activities (Yuan et al 2019, Hoton et al 2017). Majority of the influent microfibers are removed by high-performing wastewater treatment plants, But at the same time the disposed bio-solids, produced during removal process, can enter the water body through surface runoff and thus impart a significant load of plastics in

aquatic body. (Raju et al 2018). Microplastics are categorised as primary microplastics and secondary microplastics depending on their mode of origin.

3.1 Primary microplastics: They serve as raw materials for different products. Thus they originate directly from industry during their production or from the waste of the produces. Based on shape and usage, primary microplastics can further be categorised as micro beads, microfibers and plastic pellets. Products releasing primary microplastics in the environment:

1) Personal Care Products: Micro beads present in several personal care products like toothpaste, exfoliating facial scrub are important contributor of primary microplastics. They are used in materials used for makeup foundation like blush powders, eye shadow, mascara, nail polish, hair coloring. Micro beads are also used as a component of many other products like shaving cream, deodorant, sunscreen, bubble bath lotions, baby products, and insect repellents (Auta et al 2017).

2) Cleaning products: Washing textiles can release microfibers in waste water. It has been reported that 6kg of synthetic clothes in a single wash release an average of about 700,000 fibres (Napper and Thompson 2016).

3) Products from medical applications: In medicinal field, microplastics are used in dental care. Microplastics are also used as vectors for drugs in medical industry (Patel et al., 2009).

4) Other applications: In plastic production, pellets are used as a feedstock. The emission of these pellets in the atmosphere becomes a source of microplastic (Li et al 2016). The microplastics used in air blasting technology are example of primary microplastics (Auta et al 2017).

3.2 Secondary microplastics: Secondary microplastics are produced by means of fragmentation and slow degradation of plastic products in course of a number of natural processes viz, photolysis, mechanical forces, etc. A recent study shows that polystyrene that finds its use in packaging industry, readily fragments into microplastics through photo-oxidation processes (Biber et al 2019). The plastic sources like fishing nets, fish hatcheries, and offshore drilling generate secondary microplastics by long term deterioration. They directly enter the water body and become a threat to biota (Barboza et al. 2018). In agricultural field, microcapsule fertilizers used to avoid leaching of nitrate in ground water are another important source of microplastic contamination in aquatic ecosystem. Portions of microcapsules are released as secondary microplastics and go to the ocean through the paddy runoff. (Katsumi et al 2020). Microplastics shed of vehicle tyres is also one of the primary cause of microplastic pollution in the sea (Evangelidou et al 2020).

4. Toxicity

Feeding, growth, spawning and existence of aquatic organisms are significantly impacted by the presence of microplastics in waterbody. The ingestion of microplastics by biota is a common way to induce toxicological effects to organisms in aquatics (Hämer et al. 2014). The study by Cole et al (2015) showed that ingestion of microplastics significantly affect the feed habit, fertility and functioning of zooplanktons like copepods. Long term exposure of microplastics on *Calanushelgolandicus* copepod resulted in eggs of smaller sizes and reduced hatchings. Causes of toxicity of microplastics are influenced by 1) Physical properties of microplastics 2) Chemical properties of microplastics and 3) also due to the fact that pollutants adsorbed involuntarily by microplastics cause harmful reactions.

4.1 Toxicity from physical properties: Size, concentration, shape and texture influence the toxicity of microplastics. It is more likely that possibility of risk such as variance in feed habits, reduction in development is more in the species who consume greater number of

microplastics (Horton et al. 2018). Increase in concentration of microplastics can result in faecal impaction or malnutrition in mussels (Berglund et al 2019). High concentration of microplastics may cause anaemia. It also has adverse effects on the health and defence system of aquatic animals as it weakens their immune system (Hamed et al. 2019). There are several reports on size dependency of microbial toxicity. Study by Lei et al (2018b) on microplastics toxicity have shown that larger sized microplastics are found in gill and gut of zebrafish but microplastics with small sizes are accumulated also in the liver. It has also been reported that presence of small sized polystyrene microplastics disturb the fish's hepatic metabolic processes. Exposure to microsized polystyrene microplastics affect sperm mobility and ovocyte quality of Oyster (Sussarellu et al. 2016). Shape is another crucial factor that affects toxicity. Choi et al. (2018) compared the effects of spherical or irregular shaped microplastics on swimming behaviors, gene expression, and enzyme activities of sheepshead minnow (*Cyprinodon variegatus*) and reported that irregular microplastics decreased swimming ability of sheepshead minnow compared to spherical microplastics. Study by Qiao et al. (2019a, 2019b) have shown that microplastics having fibre shape get accumulated in the gut of zebrafish more than beads and fragments shaped microplastics. This resulted in more severe intestinal toxicity of fish in case of fibre shaped microplastics compared to bead and fragment microplastics. Jabeen et al. (2018) demonstrated fiber were the only plastic particles that induced several damages in the intestinal lining of goldfish. According to Au et al. (2015), polypropylene microplastic fibers are more toxic to the freshwater amphipod, *Hyalella azteca* compared to spherically shaped particles of polyethylene microplastic.

4.2 Toxicity from Chemical properties: Different types of chemical additives, such as Phthalates, bisphenol A, octylphenol, nonylphenol, polybrominated diphenyl ethers etc are used in the synthesis of microplastics (Besseling et al. 2014). These are used to improve stability, plasticity, flame retarding ability of plastic materials. Many of these substances are known endocrine disruptors. So, release of these compounds in body tissues of aquatic organisms and human being via food chain may induce several toxic effects. A toxicology study by Nobre et al. 2015 showed that the leaching of chemical additives from raw and beach-stranded microplastics into water can yield adverse and detrimental side effects on embryos as well as on well-developed organisms. Depending on the ratio of additives present in microplastics, toxicity can vary from plastic to plastic. (Botterell et al 2019).

4.3 Toxicity from noxious reaction to pollutants absorbed involuntarily by microplastics: High surface area to volume ratio, adsorption capacity and hydrophobic nature provide the microplastic to act as a possible carrier of different pollutants. Among the different pollutants, polychlorinated biphenyls, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, organo-chlorine pesticides like DDT are of special concern as some of these are persistent in nature and some of these hamper the reproductive system of organisms. The dynamics of the adsorption of these persistent organic pollutants into plastic material depends on the properties of particular polymer as well as the properties like type, hydrophobicity, density and molecular weight of the particular pollutant (da Costa et al. 2017). Some of the marine microplastics of North Sea shows the presence of bacterial strains on their surface (Kirstein et al 2016).

5. Removal of microplastics

5.1 Removal in wastewater treatment plant:

Wastewater treatment plants are considered as one of the major sources of microplastic pollution in aquatic body. Removal efficiency varies plant to plant. It is seen from several studies that preliminary and primary treatment, especially sedimentation and solids skimming can remove about 72% of plastic particles present in sewage influent whereas secondary and

tertiary treatment can remove 88% and 94% respectively, on an average, of the number of microplastic particles present in sewage influent. Membrane bioreactor demonstrated a higher potential for more effective microplastic removal, from 82.1–99.9% compared to other advanced tertiary treatment techniques (Paul et al 2020). It is observed that the majority of plastics removed during this series of treatment stages are retained in the sewage sludge which is disposed on land or reused in agricultural field. It is one of the major shortcomings of conventional waste water treatment techniques. Thus there is a possibility of plastic particles to enter into the aquatic body through surface runoff or agricultural runoff.

5.2 Removal by biological methods:

Microplastics can be biodegraded using microorganisms, marine fungi and bacterial strains. Biodegradation of microplastic depends on plastic polymer type as well as environmental parameters like sunlight, temperature, atmospheric humidity, ultraviolet rays (Shah et al. 2008). It has been shown that smaller microplastics are more easily fragmented by zooplankton in suitable environment (Ter Halle et al (2016). Fungus can degrade microplastics in presence of an enzyme (serine hydrolases) at a specific temperature under stirring. But time of degradation is higher due to the lower reaction rate (Thuhin et al 2021). Auta et al. (2017) investigated the removal of microplastics having different chemical composition with two types of Bacillus bacterial strains, *Bacillus cereus* and *Bacillus gottheilii*, isolated from mangrove sediments. The study revealed that *Bacillus gottheilii* can better degrade microplastics. Sadaf Shabbir et al (2020) introduced periphytic biofilm to decompose microplastics having different polymeric substances like polyethylene, polypropylene, polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and reported that presence of other nutrients like glucose, peptone increase the rate of degradation than using periphytic biofilm alone.

Apart from these, Bioadsorption is a promising technique to remove microplastics from water body. The study by Sundback et al (2018) has shown that edible marine microalgae, seaweed, named *Fucus vesiculosus* can adsorb microplastics due to the presence of alginic acid in its cell wall. It has been shown that biodegradable, porous sponge incorporated with chitin and graphene oxide could absorb different types of plastic particles. However, particle's surface charge strongly influence the sorption of microplastics on algal surface. The tendency to be adsorbed more efficiently is higher for positively charged microplastics (Thuhin et al 2021). Recent studies have shown that biochar can be a good adsorbing agent and removal of microplastics can be carried out effectively using biochar (Wang et al 2020, Singh et al 2021, Siipola et al 2020).

5.3 Removal by membrane filtration

Use of dynamic membrane to remove microplastics from synthetic wastewater has been reported by Li et al (2018b). Effectiveness of this process particularly depends on particle's size, concentration, influent flux and durability of membrane. Removal efficiency can be increased to 99.9%, if simple dynamic membrane can be replaced by membrane bioreactor (Talvitie et al 2017a). But the major drawback of this process is fouling of membrane.

5.4 Removal by Chemical Treatments

Coagulation-agglomeration is a common practice to separate particles from waste water. Usually, Fe and Al based salts are used as coagulant in this process. The efficiency of this process depends upon the pH, chemical composition of the media and type of coagulant used. Herbot et al (2018) suggested the use of alkoxysilanes (tetraethoxysilane) for the treatment of

microplastics originating from textile and cosmetic industries.

Recently, studies are carried out on the use of advanced oxidation processes, particularly photocatalytic degradation to remove microplastics. Use of different photocatalysts like rod-like ZnO nanoparticles, protein-based N-TiO₂, photoactive micromotor has been reported in removal of microplastics. Au-decorated TiO₂-based micromotor can remove polystyrene microplastics from wastewater under UV radiation (Wang et al 2019). Protein-based N-TiO₂ photocatalysts are used in degradation of the polyethylene microplastics present in solid and aqueous phases, as reported by Ariza-Tarazona et al. (2019). Investigation by Tofa et al (2019) on heterogeneous photocatalytic degradation of microplastics with polyethylene of lower densities using rod-like ZnO nanoparticles revealed the formation of new compounds on degradation.

Conclusion:

This mini review depicts the extent to which microplastic pollution is getting spread in the environment. Many literatures are available on the toxicity of microplastics to aquatic organisms and human health. But pathway of toxicity i.e how the microplastics affect the body tissues of aquatic organisms and human health are not clear. A deeper investigation is needed in this regard. After literature survey on various removal methods it can be concluded that i) it is very difficult to scale up all the reported processes ii) effective removal of microorganisms can be carried out by sorption and filtration iii) Incorporation of membrane bioreactor increases removal efficiency to 99% but this process leads to secondary pollution. This suggests more research on removal techniques of microplastics from aquatic body.

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